

SITE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA F	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.5045 Max: 63.5278	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 5017 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropogenic	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No
In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No		In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No		Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 2537-2540		Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No
DEFINITION Construction cut of wall 5018				Covered by ☐ SU	Fills ☐ SU	Filled by SU: 5016
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☒ Composition ☐ Compaction		FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☐ Construction ☒ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive		
Anthropic ☐ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass		Geological ☐ Tuff (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)		Organic ☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)		
				Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft		
				Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)		

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: _____ Is bound to (only for masonry): _____

Is abuted by: _____ Abuts: _____

Is covered by: _____ Covers: _____

Is cut by: _____ Cuts: 5004

Is filled by: 5016 Fills: _____

OBSERVATIONS
Excavated on dry sunny day with good visibility

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: along South Eastern Area F excavation limit (along wall SU 5018)
Shape: long rectangle

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions): _____
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): _____
 Observations about thickness (increases? Decreases?): _____
 Name of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:
cut bottom slopes up from south to north. there is a steep down in the cut bottom towards the southern corner

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petrus-appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 5017 cuts through SU 5004 and appears to represent a construction cut for a later phase of wall 5018.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by EK SJL

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Entered by

on